

RESOURCE USE PATTERN AND RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY OF FARMING SYSTEMS IN WESTERN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Resource use efficiency of farming systems plays a pivotal role in the resource productivity. Present study delves into the resource use efficiency of selected farming systems in the Western Maharashtra. Three farming systems were selected from western Maharashtra region viz. Crops only farming system (F.S. I), Crops plus Livestock farming system (F.S. II), Crops plus Livestock plus Horticulture farming system (F.S. III). Assessment of resource use pattern shows that, across all three farming systems, labor was the major expense. In system II, livestock was the second major expense, while in systems I and III, machinery was the second major expense. Other expenses like fertilizers, seeds, and irrigation were relatively smaller. The study used the Cobb-Douglas production function to estimate resource use efficiency across irrigated and rainfed regions. Labor, land, fertilizers, and working capital were significant factors influencing output in various systems. The sum of elasticities exceeded one, indicating increasing returns to scale in all farming systems. Specific factors with the most significant impact varied across systems and regions. Land under horticulture crops played a prominent role in farming system III.

Keywords: Resource use pattern, Resource use efficiency, Farming systems

Introduction

Farming system is a mixture of farm enterprises such as crop, livestock, apiculture, agro-forestry and fruit crops. In these farming systems family allocates its resources. The resource use pattern of any production activity indicates composition of the expenditures incurred on various inputs. It is useful to locate the strengths and weaknesses in the production system so as to increase the efficiency of inputs. The quantities of various inputs used directly affected the cost of cultivation and therefore, per farm and per hectare utilization of inputs such as human labour, bullock power, seeds, manures, fertilizers, machine hrs., plant protection charges, irrigation charges and livestock maintenance etc., have been studied in physical and monetary terms.

This study, "Economic analysis of farming systems in Western Maharashtra," delves into the resource use efficiency of selected farming systems in the region. Three farming systems were selected from western Maharashtra region viz. Crops only farming system (F.S. I), Crops plus Livestock farming system (F.S. II), Crops plus Livestock plus Horticulture farming system (F.S. III). Thus, the present study investigates the resource use patterns and resource use efficiencies of selected farming systems in western Maharashtra.

Materials And Methods**Sample Selection**

Primary data for the year 2018-19 was collected from 240 sample farmers in the four districts of Ahmednagar, Nashik, Pune, and Sangli in Western Maharashtra region using a personal interview method with specially designed schedules. The three widely adopted farming systems were selected for the study: I) Crops only, II) Crops + Livestock, III) Crops + Livestock + Horticulture crops.

Analysis of data:

The data was analyzed with the help of tabular as well as various statistical tools. For assessing quantitatively objectives and

Table 1 Per hectare resource use pattern under farming system I

hypotheses outlined for the present study, following analytical tools and techniques.

Tabular analysis

Tabular analysis involving the computation of means, percentages etc. were employed to present the data regarding the socio-economic profile, cropping systems, enterprise analysis, costs and returns, employment generation, constraints and opinion expressed by the farmers.

Functional analysis (Cobb- Douglas type production function: The resource use efficiency was studied for different farming systems by fitting Cobb-Douglas type of production function to data for three farming systems. Gross returns of the farm was the dependent variable, whereas independent variables. The returns to scale was estimated directly by using the sum of 'bi' coefficients. The return was increasing, constant or diminishing based on whether the value of summation of 'bi' is greater, equal or less than unity, respectively. The coefficient of multiple determination (R²) was used to measure the proportion of variation in output explained by the independent variables.

Marginal Value Product (MVP) to Marginal Factor Cost (MFC) ratio: Resource is said to be optimally allocated when its Marginal Value Product (MVP) is equal to Marginal Factor Cost (MFC).

Results And Discussions**Farming System I****Resource Use pattern**

In farming system I, the average per farm cash expenditure was ₹ 88,941 at the overall level. The major share in the total expenditure was labour charges, which shared 42.36 per cent, followed by more machine charges (21.56 %) indicated the use of tractor, then fertilizers (11.68 %), seed (8.90 %), manures (7.20 %) and irrigation charges (5.30 %).

(Crops Only)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Irrigated region		Rainfed Region		Overall	
		Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹
1.	Hired Human labour (Mandays)	120.01	22400.78 (29.71)	57.07	9568.33 (21.55)	88.54	15984.56 (26.69)
2.	Family labour (Mandays)	52.06	10283.78 (13.64)	48.41	8496.30 (19.13)	50.24	9390.04 (15.68)
	Total labour (Mandays)	172.07	32684.56 (43.35)	105.49	18064.63 (40.68)	138.78	25374.59 (42.36)
3.	Seed (q)	-	7920.18 (10.51)	-	2742.53 (6.18)	-	5331.35 (8.90)
4.	Manure (q)	31.29	5363.51 (7.11)	14.20	3256.52 (7.33)	22.74	4310.01 (7.20)
5.	Fertilizers (kg.)	320.46	8894.28 (11.80)	206.68	5095.30 (11.47)	263.57	6994.79 (11.68)
6.	Machine (hrs.)	21.15	13746.22	18.59	12086.91	19.87	12916.57

			(18.23)		(27.22)		(21.56)
7.	Plant protection (₹)	-	1171.66 (1.55)	-	1015.05 (2.29)	-	1093.35 (1.83)
8.	Irrigation charges (₹)	-	5092.16 (6.75)	-	1253.67 (2.82)	-	3172.92 (5.30)
9.	Livestock maintenance (feed cost, vet. charges)	-	519.66 (0.69)	-	894.23 (2.01)	-	706.94 (1.18)
	Total	-	75392.23 (100)	-	44408.84 (100)	-	59900.54 (100)

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total)

Resource use efficiency

The Cobb-Douglas type of production function was found to be the good fit to the data. The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) indicated the proportion of total variation in the dependent variable (output) explained by the independent variables jointly.

In farming system I, the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) of irrigated region was 0.83. The expenditure on fertilizer (X_2) and land under agronomical crop (X_1) were significant at 1 per cent level, while expenditure on FYM (X_3) and other working capital (X_5) were statistically significant at 5 per cent level. The sum of elasticities was 1.57 indicating increasing returns to scale. In rainfed region, the

coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.76. The working capital (X_5) was observed to be most positively influencing variable with regression coefficient of 0.12. While the expenditure on fertilizers (X_2) was significant at 10 per cent level. The sum of elasticities was 1.11 indicating increasing returns.

In irrigated region, the resources such as expenditure on fertilizer (X_3), FYM (X_4) and working capital (X_6) were less used as the ratios of MVP to MFC were greater than unity in farming system I. In rainfed region, the resources such as fertilizers and working capital showed more than unity of MVP to MFC ratio indicating less use of fertilizer and capital in farming system I.

Table 2 Results of Cobb - Douglas production function and MVP to MFC ratios for irrigated and rainfed farming system I

Sr. No.	Particulars	Parameter	Irrigated region		Rainfed region	
			Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios	Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios
1	Intercept	a	-0.6180		8.315	
2	Land under agronomical crops (ha.)	X_1	0.350*** (0.213)	0.0029	0.611 (0.810)	0.82
3	Fertilizer expenditure (₹)	X_2	0.208*** (0.075)	36.12	0.092* (0.045)	44.82
4	FYM expenditures (₹)	X_3	0.182** (0.089)	1.79	0.220 (0.710)	1.16
5	Expenditure on human labour (₹)	X_4	0.239 (0.144)	1.41	0.066 (0.191)	1.37
6	Other working capital (₹)	X_5	0.772** (0.329)	85.6	0.128*** (0.014)	2.65
	R^2			0.83		0.76
	Return to scale			1.57		1.11

(Figures in parentheses are the respective standard errors)

*, **, *** indicate significance at 10, 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively

Farming System II

Resource Use pattern

In farming system II, the average per farm cash expenditure was ₹ 2,17,337 at the overall level. The major portion in the total

expenditure was on human labour, which shared 47.99 per cent, followed by total livestock (29.12 %), machine (8.50 %), fertilizers (4.74 %), seed (3.40 %), manures (2.99 %) and irrigation charges (2.41 %).

Table 3 Per hectare resource use pattern under farming system II

(Crops + Livestock)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Irrigated region		Rainfed Region		Overall	
		Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹
1	Hired Human labour (Mandays)	101.36	19844.13 (11.64)	50.18	9083.20 (7.77)	75.77	14463.67 (10.06)
2	Family labour (Mandays)	70.20	14193.33 (8.33)	63.01	11867.25 (10.15)	66.60	13030.29 (9.07)
	Labour for Livestock (Mandays)	257.97	50176.00 (29.43)	177.98	32782.01 (28.02)	217.98	41479.01 (28.86)
	Total labour (Mandays)	429.53	84213.47 (49.40)	291.17	53732.47 (45.94)	360.35	68972.97 (47.99)
3	Seed (kg.)	-	7378.55 (4.33)	-	2397.83 (2.05)	-	4888.19 (3.40)
4	Manure (q)	35.65	5948.33 (3.49)	11.54	2646.78 (2.26)	23.59	4297.56 (2.99)
5	Fertilizers (kg.)	255.64	8921.37 (5.23)	186.49	4705.25 (4.02)	221.07	6813.31 (4.74)
6	Machine charges (₹)	18.83	12620.13 (7.40)	17.61	11801.21 (10.09)	18.22	12210.67 (8.50)
7	Plant protection (₹)	-	1446.22 (0.85)	-	987.77 (0.84)	-	1217.00 (0.85)

8	Irrigation charges (₹)	-	5367.17 (3.15)	-	1569.95 (1.34)	-	3468.56 (2.41)
9	Livestock maintenance (feed cost, vet. Charges)	-	44574.31 (26.15)	-	39133.26 (33.45)	-	41853.79 (29.12)
	Total	-	170469.56 (100)	-	116974.53 (100)	-	143722.05 (100)

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total)

Resource Use efficiency

In farming system II, the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) of irrigated region was 0.84. The human labour (X_4), feed and fodder (X_7) and number of goat/sheep (X_9) were found to be influencing inputs with regression coefficients of 0.437, 0.560 and 0.036. The sum of elasticities was greater than unity (1.59). In rainfed region, the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.78. The feed and fodder (X_7) and number of goat/sheep (X_9) were found to be the most

influencing input with regression coefficient of 0.678 and 0.019. The sum of elasticities was 1.29 indicated increasing returns to scale. In irrigated region, the ratios of MVP to MFC were greater than unity for the resources such as fertilizer (7.38), human labour (8.22), numbers of goat/sheep (4.66) and feed and fodder (1.84). While in rainfed region, the ratio of MVP to MFC were greater than unity in case of feed and fodder and number of sheep/ goat, indicating less use of these resources and production can be increased by increasing use of these resources

Table 4 Results of Cobb - Douglas production function coefficients and MVP to MFC ratios for irrigated and rainfed region farming system II

Sr. No.	Particulars	Parameter	Irrigated region		Rainfed region	
			Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios	Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios
1	Intercept	a	2.580		2.223	
2	Land under agronomical crops (ha.)	X_1	0.108 (0.099)	1.71	0.102 (0.111)	0.97
3	Milch Animals (Cows, buffalos no.)	X_2	0.050 (0.074)	1.14	0.058 (0.100)	5.91
4	Fertilizer expenditure (₹)	X_3	0.217** (0.098)	7.38	0.106 (0.140)	95.96
5	Farm yard manure expenditures (₹)	X_4	0.004 (0.007)	7.30	0.010 (0.007)	8.02
6	Expenditure on human labour (₹)	X_5	0.437*** (0.099)	8.22	0.016 (0.243)	1.04
7	Other working capital (₹)	X_6	0.219 (0.189)	0.72	0.292 (0.367)	0.78
8	Feed and Fodder (₹)	X_7	0.560*** (0.049)	1.84	0.678*** (0.092)	70.33
9	Poultry Bird (No.)	X_8	0.004 (0.006)	44.40	0.009 (0.007)	5.59
10	Goat / Sheep (No.)	X_9	0.036*** (0.012)	4.66	0.019** (0.008)	29.47
	R^2		0.84		0.78	
	Return to scale		1.59		1.29	

(Figures in parentheses are the respective standard errors)

*, **, *** indicate significance at 10, 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively

Farming System Iii

Resource Use pattern

In farming system III, the average per farm cash expenditure was ₹ 4,89,640 at the overall level. The human labour charges cost constituted major portion of the total expenditure which shared 46.81

per cent, followed by livestock maintenance (24.52 %) and manure expenses (5.81 %), machine charges (5.77 %), fertilizers (5.78 %), plant protection (5.50 %), irrigation charges (3.35 %) and seed (2.47 %), respectively.

Table 5 Per hectare resource use pattern under farming system III

(Crops + Livestock + Horticulture)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Irrigated region		Rainfed Region		Overall	
		Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹	Qty.	₹
1	Hired Human labour (Mandays)	144.09	32519.01 (13.63)	111.89	23422.58 (13.71)	127.99	27970.79 (13.66)
2	Family labour (Mandays)	65.63	15111.77 (6.33)	60.20	13045.56 (7.64)	62.91	14078.66 (6.88)
	Labour for Livestock (Mandays)	294.19	64620.38 (27.08)	205.31	42927.47 (25.13)	249.75	53773.93 (26.27)
	Total labour (Mandays)	503.90	112251.16 (47.05)	377.40	79395.61 (46.47)	440.65	95823.39 (46.81)
3	Seed (kg.)	-	5317.67 (2.23)	-	4784.09 (2.80)	-	5050.88 (2.47)
4	Manure (q)	46.81	14856.10 (6.23)	37.33	8942.09 (5.23)	42.07	11899.10 (5.81)
5	Fertilizers (kg.)	227.12	14495.70 (6.08)	133.28	9162.86 (5.36)	180.20	11829.28 (5.78)

6	Machine (hrs.)	18.75	12752.27 (5.34)	15.99	10873.39 (6.36)	17.37	11812.83 (5.77)
7	Plant protection (₹)	-	13699.04 (5.74)	-	8826.58 (5.17)	-	11262.81 (5.50)
8	Irrigation charges (₹)	-	8393.41 (3.52)	-	5308.78 (3.11)	-	6851.09 (3.35)
9	Livestock maintenance (feed cost, vet. charges)	-	56836.27 (23.82)	-	43550.13 (25.49)	-	50193.20 (24.52)
	Total	-	238601.61 (100)	-	170843.54 (100)	-	204722.57 (100)

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total)

Resource Use Efficiency

In farming system III, the coefficient of multiple determination (R²) of irrigated region was 0.81. The land under horticultural crops (X₁₀) was found positive and significantly influencing gross returns with regression coefficient of 0.421 which indicated that one per cent increase in land under horticultural crops (X₁₀) will result into 0.421 per cent increase in the gross returns. The working capital (X₆) and

fertilizer expenditure (X₃) were found significant at 5 and 10 per cent level. The sum of elasticities was 2.55. In rainfed region, the coefficient of multiple determination (R²) was 0.73. The land under horticulture crops was significant at 5 per cent level while milch animal (X₂), fertilizers expenditures (X₃) and FYM expenditure (X₄) were significant at 10 per cent level, respectively. The sum of elasticities was 2.47, indicating increasing returns to scale.

Table 6 Results of Cobb - Douglas production function coefficients and MVP to MFC ratios for irrigated region and rainfed region farming system III

Sr. No.	Particulars	Parameter	Irrigated region		Rainfed region	
			Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios	Regression coefficient	MVP : MFC Ratios
1	Intercept	a	24.68		14.71	
2	Land under agronomical crops (ha.)	X ₁	0.021 (0.065)	0.45	0.050 (0.097)	9.28
3	Milch Animals (cows, buffalos no.)	X ₂	0.617 (1.346)	4.54	0.193* (0.088)	1.01
4	Fertilizer expenditure (₹)	X ₃	0.651* (0.323)	4.08	0.380* (0.205)	3.08
5	Farm yard manure expenditures (₹)	X ₄	0.033 (0.022)	1.06	0.223* (0.128)	96.04
6	Total Expenditure on human labour (₹)	X ₅	0.079 (0.060)	5.21	0.014 (1.535)	1.28
7	Other working capital (₹)	X ₆	0.460** (0.206)	7.49	0.200 (1.487)	66.02
9	Feed and Fodder (₹)	X ₇	0.252 (1.035)	10.31	0.638 (0.481)	6.64
8	Poultry Bird (No.)	X ₈	0.001 (0.013)	3.58	0.021 (0.012)	0.81
9	Sheep / Goat (No.)	X ₉	0.013 (0.025)	7.9	0.050 (0.013)	0.70
10	Land under horticultural crops (ha.)	X ₁₀	0.421*** (0.080)	5.38	0.305** (0.142)	5.16
	R ²		0.81		0.73	
	Return to scale		2.55		2.47	

(Figures in parentheses are the respective standard errors)

*, **, *** indicate significance at 10, 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively

In farming system III, the ratio of MVP to MFC was also greater than unity for the resources such as land under horticultural crops, expenditure on fertilizer and working capital indicating less use of these resources. In rainfed region the resource such as expenditure on fertilizer, FYM expenditure and land under horticulture crops showed more than unity of the MVP to MFC ratio indicating less use of the resources. Similar findings were reported by Vishweshwar (1994), Nagraj et al. (1996), Varma (2002), Rajeshwari (2004), Dorge (2010) and Pawar and Vijaykumar (2012).

Conclusion

The study investigated resource use in different farming systems. Human labor was the primary cost across all systems, while livestock maintenance was crucial in systems II and III. Machine use and fertilizer were significant inputs in all systems. The specific factors influencing resource use efficiency differed between farming systems. All farming systems exhibited increasing returns, and resources were generally underutilized, as indicated by MVP/MFC ratios exceeding one.

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